

A Kinetic Study of the Oxidation of Malonic Acid by Cerium (IV)

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The kinetics of oxidation of malonic acid by cerium (IV) in sulphuric acid medium is found to be of first order with respect to each reactant. The first-order rate constant is found to vary inversely as sulphuric acid concentration. The Arrhenius equation is found to be valid between 20° and 30°. The values for the energy of activation, entropy of activation, frequency factor, and temperature coefficient are found to be 11,962 g. cal./mole, -19.24 cal./MÅ, $4.124 \times 10^8 \text{ sec}^{-1}$, and 1.901 respectively. These experimental findings are consistent with the fact that the mechanism involves the rapid formation of complex by the reactant which slowly decomposes to provide Ce(III) and free radical. The active free radical is found to be as $\text{CH}(\text{CO}_2\text{H})_2$, capable of oxidising formic, acetic, and succinic acids, which are not oxidised by Ce(IV). The reaction mechanism on the basis of induced radical oxidation and of a simple method of quantitative estimation of formic acid in presence of inorganic salt is suggested.

The kinetics of oxidation of malonic acid by cerium(IV) has not been so far studied. The present investigation is therefore undertaken to elucidate the kinetics of malonic acid oxidation by Ce(IV).

EXPERIMENTAL

The chemicals used were either 'AnalaR' or E. Merck's guaranteed reagent quality. Equal volume (50 ml) of ceric sulphate (in known sulphuric acid concentration) and malonic acid solution of known concentrations were brought to the same temperature in a thermostat (maintained to $\pm 0.01^\circ$) and then mixed. The course of the reaction was followed by immediately withdrawing a known volume (10 ml) of the reaction mixture at definite intervals into ice-cold water to quench the reaction velocity. The unchanged ceric ion was quickly titrated with a standard Mohr's salt solution, using ferroin as an indicator.

The active species of ceric sulphate involved in the present investigation in the given range of H_2SO_4 is $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2^+$.

TABLE I

Dependence of rate on Ce(IV) at 25°.

$10^3[\text{Malonic acid}] = 5.0M$. $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 2.0M$.

$10^3[\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2](M)$	..	25.000	16.660	12.500	10.000
$10^3 k_1(\text{sec}^{-1})$	..	0.4802	0.8348	0.6829	0.7344

TABLE II

Dependence of rate on malonic acid at 20°.

 $10^3 [\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2] = 5.0M$. $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 2.0M$.

$10^3[\text{Malonic acid}](M)$	25.00	16.66	12.50	10.00
$10^3 k_1 (\text{sec}^{-1})$	3.007	2.049	1.449	1.117
$\frac{k_1 (\text{sec}^{-1})}{[\text{Malonic acid}]}$	0.120	0.121	0.116	0.112

TABLE III

Values of first-order rate constant at diff. malonic acid conc. and temp.

 $10^3 [\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2] = 5.0M$. $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 2.01M$

$10^3[\text{Malonic acid}]$.	20°.	$10^3 k_1 (\text{sec}^{-1})$ at 25°.	30°.
25.00 M.	3.007	4.737	5.943
16.66	2.049	2.805	3.985
12.55	1.449	1.769	2.660
10.00	1.117	1.458	1.895

DISCUSSION

The reaction has been found to be of first order with respect to cerium (IV) and malonic acid, as shown in Tables I and II.

FIG. 1. "Unit reaction time" vs. "time" at 25°.

 $[\text{Malonic acid}]$ & $[\text{CeSO}_4)_2] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3}M$ $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 2.0M$.Slope = $n/2$. Intercept = $1/K_0^{n-1}$. $\therefore 10^4 k_2 = 1.428 \text{ litre/mole}^{-1}/\text{sec.}^{-1}$ FIG. 2. Plot of $1/k_1$ vs. $1/[\text{Malonic acid}]$ at 25°.

The total order of the reaction is found to be two, being unity with respect to each reactant. Fig. 1, obtained (when the concentration of the reactants are in equimolar proportion) by plotting "unit reaction time" against "time elapsed," not only confirms the

above fact but also provides the values of the velocity constant for the second-order reaction:

The reaction sequence is found to obey the following equation, based on the theory of Duke³:

$$-\frac{d[\text{Ce(IV)}]}{dt} = \frac{k'K[\text{Acid}][\text{Ce(IV)}]}{1 + K[\text{Acid}]}$$

where $k'K = k_1$ and $K = 1/\alpha$ is a measure of the stability complex. The slope and intercept of the curve (Fig. 2), obtained by plotting the reciprocal of the rate constant against the reciprocal of malonic acid concentration, provides the value of $1/k'K$ and $1/k'$ respectively. The value of 11.80 is obtained from the slope and that of the equilibrium constant is 7.63.

Thus the slope and intercept of the curve are helpful in obtaining the values of equilibrium constant and the apparent first-order rate constant for the formation and decomposition of the intermediate respectively.

Inhibiting Action of Sulphuric Acid.—An inhibiting effect is observed on the reaction velocity on increasing the concentration of H_2SO_4 . The rate of the reaction is found to vary inversely as concentration of the acid.

TABLE IV

Rate dependence on H_2SO_4 concentration.

10^3 [Malonic acid] = 10.0M. 10^3 [$\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$] = 5.0M. Temp. = 25°.

$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$.	$10^3 k_1 \text{sec}^{-1}$.	$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]10^3 k_1 \text{sec}^{-1}$.	$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$	$10^3 k_1 \text{sec}^{-1}$.	$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]10^3 k_1 \text{sec}^{-1}$.
0.75M	2.520	1.8900	1.75M	1.480	2.5900
1.00	2.025	2.0250	2.00	1.377	2.7540
1.25	1.849	2.3112	2.25	1.356	3.0510
1.50	1.515	2.2725	2.50	1.127	2.8175

It appears that the inhibitory effect observed on increasing the concentration of H_2SO_4 may be mainly due to bisulphate ion, by forming $\text{HCe}(\text{SO}_4)_3^-$.

The Salt Effect.—The effect of addition of neutral salts, e.g. ammonium sulphate, sodium sulphate, has been summarised in Table V.

TABLE V

Effect of salt on the reaction velocity at 25°.

10^3 [Malonic acid] = 6.66M. 10^3 [$\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$] = 3.33M. $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ = 1.33M.

10^3 [Salt].	$10^3 k_1 \text{sec}^{-1}$	
	Na_2SO_4 .	$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$.
0.00M	1.2320	1.2320
4.16	1.1745	1.2296
8.33	1.1022	1.1960
16.33	0.9304	0.9900
33.33	0.8239	0.7832

Thus sodium sulphate and ammonium sulphate exhibit retarding effect.

The first-order rate constant at different temperatures for a particular concentration of ceric salt and different malonic acid concentrations are recorded in Table III. The straight line curves were obtained by plotting $\log k_1$ (for different concentrations of malonic acid) against the reciprocal of absolute temperatures. The Arrhenius equation is therefore valid between 20° and 30° and thus the average value for the energy of activation is found to be 11,962 g. cal./mole.

The values for the frequency factor, entropy of activation, and temperature coefficient are found to be $4.124 \times 10^8 \text{ sec}^{-1}$, $-19.24 \text{ cal./M}^\ddagger$, and 1.961 respectively.

Malonic acid on oxidation afforded formic acid, which was estimated volumetrically from the reaction products.

The method used by Shorter *et al.*⁴ appears to be tedious one, as it requires titration in hot alkaline solution with potassium permanganate after complete removal of cerous ions and the results require verification from control experiments; moreover, if the solution is strongly heated, the unusual reaction takes place.

The decomposition is facilitated in presence of sodium hydroxide, carbonate, or oxalate at a considerably lower temperature. Therefore in order to overcome the above difficulties, the following simple volumetric method, which can be satisfactorily carried out in presence of inorganic salt, is suggested.

The known volume of the reaction mixture is exactly neutralised with a standard NaOH solution and then heated. Excess of bromine water is added till the colour persisted; the excess of bromine is then removed by boiling. The hydrobromic acid thus liberated is titrated against the standard NaOH solution, using phenolphthalein as an indicator. The overall equation may be written as

[Found: 3.997 equivalent of cerium (IV) per mole of malonic acid]

Malonic acid oxidation by cerium(IV) involves only tartronic and glyoxylic acids as intermediates because mesoxalic and oxalic acids are completely and immediately oxidised by cerium (IV) to carbon dioxide and the oxidation of glycollic acid is much slower than the malonic acid; so had it been formed, the oxidation rate would have decreased considerably. Its oxidation is postulated as:

That malonic acid is oxidised through free radical formation has been confirmed by mercuric chloride reduction and polymerisation tests⁵; the active free radical is found to be

4. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3276.

5. Drummond and Waters, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 2836.

$\cdot\text{CH}(\text{CO}_2\text{H})_2$ capable of oxidising formic, acetic, and succinic acids. It is found that these acids are not oxidised by ceric sulphate, but when malonic acid and ceric sulphate are mixed together and a few drops of this mixture [containing $\cdot\text{CH}(\text{CO}_2\text{H})_2$] are added to the mixture of ceric sulphate and any one of these acids, then the oxidation takes place easily. But in the present investigation, formic acid is found to be the ultimate product, indicating that the free radical $\cdot\text{CH}(\text{CO}_2\text{H})_2$ does not remain as such to that stage.

Formation of the stable activated complex and its slow decomposition providing free radical and cerium(III), which is of kinetically first order, and the chain mechanism involving free radical are evident from the negative value of entropy of activation and frequency factor⁶ of order less than 10^{10} sec^{-1} .

The foregoing information accords the following mechanism, which is in agreement with the oxidation of malonic acid by manganic pyrophosphate proposed by Drummond *et al*⁷.

Thanks are due to Sri P. K. Singhal for his help in the course of these investigations.

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Received June 5, 1963.

6. Glasstone, "Text Book of Physical Chemistry", Macmillan & Co. Ltd., London, 2nd ed., 1960, p. 1110.
7. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2456.